

Research Article

The Place of Cultural Economy in Development Policies of Developing Countries: Van Province

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Abstract

Van city has serious socio-economic cultural development problems. Despite these problems, Van's cultural and natural diversity, as well as its potential to be an important commercial center due to its geopolitical situation, are important for the solution of extant problems. In this regard, this paper strives to examine the challenges of Van from the cultural aspect. Accordingly; in Van, the investments determined by the actors affecting the development and planning process periodically (2003-2016) were evaluated vis-à-vis the classification of cultural economy and human development index. Content analysis was used in the research. The European Union (EU) is one of the international actors in Van and the national actors are; Ministry of Development, Ministry of Interior, Ministry of Culture and Tourism, T.C. Prime Ministry General Directorate of Foundations, Eastern Anatolia Project (EAP) Regional Development Administration, Eastern Anatolia Development Agency (EADA) and Municipalities. It is seen that these are important actors in development policies and the investments they have made coincide with the strategies they have targeted. International actors prioritize social and human development investments within the framework of EU regional development policies. National actors however followed both a development model within the scope of industry, trade and services, which was predominantly based on the economic perspective, and a development model from the tourism perspective in the services class. Consequently, it is seen that development in Van is not directly evaluated from the cultural view, but evaluated together with tourism, culture is instrumentalized for tourism and cultural tourism is brought to the fore and cultural policies are developed from the tourism perspective.

Keywords: development, human development, cultural economy and culture based urban strategies, actors, Turkey, Van

1. Introduction

Development aims at the improvement and progress of a country primarily in economic, then cultural and social dimensions. Development theories define which types of capital should be prioritized by analyzing the economic structure of countries over capital types and define them according to different types of capital in different theoretical framework. In the historical process, the concept of development, which is shaped by labor-oriented physical capital, has shifted to human capital and social capital approaches based on knowledge and social networks with the realization of scientific and technological revolution. Among these approaches, human capital puts the cultural and social dimensions at the center of development along with the economic dimension.

In Van, where the development problem is experienced in economic, cultural and social dimensions, it is important to determine the extent to which the actors evaluate the development approach in their development policies and investments towards the city. In particular, due to the impact of globalization and economic crises, cities in competition have turned to urban development policies aimed at the economic structuring of information, technology, creativity and cultural aspects. Among these policies, culture-based urban strategies based on the cultural economy, aim to increase the global competitiveness of cities and to ensure economic recovery. The culture is considered an important tool in development and provides a serious economic return. In this context this research aims to pinpoint the understanding of development in the national, regional and local policies of Van province, in which sectors the culture is included, and which actors are more effective in investments towards sectors. The research; who influenced development policies (actors), how they affected (directly / indirectly), what tools they used (grants / support / investment programs, strategy plans), how they viewed culture (how they defined culture) and what their effects were (investment amounts and its share in the total investment) seeks answers.

1.1. Human Development and Human Development Index

The concept of development is used mostly in terms of growth, development and progress in relation to the economy, but it also includes social and cultural development. Development institutions are shaped according to physical, economic, cultural, social and human capital types. In neoclassical economic theories, growth/development/improvement has been evaluated more in terms of quantity and economic development has been prioritized. It is emphasized that in addition to quantity, quality is also important with the theories of internal growth and human capital plays a pivotal role in economic development. Information and technology have been defined as a developing structure with human capital and it is stated that there is a direct proportional relationship between these three components and economic development [1]; [2]. Bourdieu defined these capitals as economic, social, cultural and

symbolic [3]. Bourdieu defined “cultural capital” as the structure which is ingrained by the possessors of power in a field into families and individuals through education. This structure is also seen as “information capital” [4].

The theoretical background of human development is based on Amartya Sen’s capability approach. Sen stated that the increase of national income can be an effective tool for expanding freedoms, but they are also affected by different social and economic elements such as education, health services, political and individual freedoms. He stated that having income and knowledge and having a healthy life are the basic elements that enable the individual to go to the social field. He indicated that the material wealth of the countries is not enough to meet the personal development of the individual or the richness of his life. Therefore, when evaluating the level of development of the countries, the economic data is not sufficient per se, and it is important to know how and to what extent the wealth created is reflected on the quality of life of the individual. At this point, whether the national economic existence creates development opportunities for individuals is taken as the primary question [5]. As a result of the capability approach, the understanding of development shifted from the basic needs of the individual to education, health, human abilities, opportunities and behaviors. According to this, the individual's ability and freedom of choice is the focus of development ([6]; [7]; [8]; [9]; [10]).

The concept of human development argues that the problem of development cannot be evaluated not only in the economic dimension but also shaped by social, cultural and human capital. According to this understanding, human being becomes the capital itself and increases the quality of the capital with accumulations (such as education, knowledge, skills, etc.) resulting in constituting the main source of production and increasing its quality [11]; [12]; [13]; [2].

As educated and healthy individuals as human capital, positively affect the quality and quantity of labor required for development, education and health have an important impact on human development understanding. Accordingly, the development criterion for improvement shaped by human capital has been evaluated within the framework of these two main factors and started to be measured with the human “development index developed” by UDNP over time as a “long and healthy life”, “access to information” and “a good standard of living” [2]; [14]; [15]; [16]; [17]; [18]; [19]. UNDP has established human development index according to three criteria by stating that human knowledge, health and lifestyle shape human capital and constitutes human improvement.

A human-centered approach is used in human development. According to this approach, it is believed that any investment in human beings will have positive results in economic growth. Accordingly, education investments made for human capital

enrich the cultural capital of individuals directly because knowledge forms the basis of cultural capital and information is mainly provided by education.

1.2. The Role of Cultural Economy in Economic Development

Culture, which is seen as a tool of economic development, has been mainly evaluated in the Western literature with the discourses of cultural and creative industries. In this context, within the study, it is aimed to reveal the relationship between cultural policies and cultural economy by evaluating culture in economic and political perspective.

Culture, which has different functions in economic, social and political terms, creates different lifestyles, maintains and promotes cultural diversity, creates social cohesion and trust in the society, better education, self-confidence and pride of belonging to a community with a history. So, culture is crucial in these social and political aspects. In addition, it is considered one of the most important tools of growth and development policies today due to its contribution to the production of goods and services with high economic value, enrichment of consumption activities, and increase in income and employment [20]. Notwithstanding the several dimensions of culture, it is often seen in academic debates as to how diversity in the urban agenda connects with planning and development, together with heritage and creative industries [21]. In this regard, the emerging cultural economy is defined as all economic activities carried out by the public or private sector towards cultural heritage, creative arts and cultural industries and is associated with the behaviors of producers, consumers and the state in the cultural industry [22].

Gibson and Kong [23] defined the cultural economy in four different areas as sectoral defining approach, labor market and production organization approach, creative index approach and convergence approach. Pratt [24] sees cultural economy as a sub-sector of the economy and states that the part of the economy related to the production of cultural goods and services represents the cultural economy. Accordingly, cultural economy is viewed as a factor with positive contributions. In the academic literature, cultural economics is evaluated together with the concepts of cultural industries, creative industries, culture and creative industries and creative economics which are discussed extensively.

Adorno and Horkheimer's book "Culture Industry", published in 1947, introduced the concept of culture industry into academic literature. It is then developed by The Department for Digital, Culture, Media and Sport (DMCS) [25] concept of the sectoral classification of cultural industries (fashion design, museums and art galleries, crafts, arts, antiquities and performance arts). Landry's [26] discourse of creative cities, Florida's [27] creative class theory with 3T defined as tolerance, technology and talent, and UNCTAD's [28] concepts of cultural economy (cultural heritage, art, media and

functional creativity) and the concept of Culture Industry has been transformed into an economic structure.

Creative industries have formed an important ecosystem in strengthening the cultural policies. In the transition of countries to knowledge society, cultural policies are reshaped by taking creative industries at the very center [29]. Dörry et al., [30] state that creative industries create economic hope for cities on the basis of two reasons. First, the spatial accumulation of human creativity gives leeway to competitive advantage of cities in global competition. Second, creative industries present an essential space for local policy action.

In this research, cultural economy is considered the field of activity, industry and services where creativity, intellectual and cultural capital are the main inputs. Cultural economy has been examined under four main headings as cultural heritage, arts, cultural industries and creative services [31].

1.3. Culture Based Urban Planning and Urban Strategies

There are various approaches and discussions about the culture-based urban planning process. These discussions are summarized under three headings by Durmaz [32]. The first area of the discussion is the renewal of urban quarters or attracting large-scale investments in places around the city, the second area is whether the policy and design intervention is at the required level, and the third is whether an investment has been made for the construction of the site or the quality of the space, or whether the strategy of branding the site (place branding) has been developed. According to these approaches, Durmaz [32] evaluated cultural planning in urban/suburban areas (inner city of peripheries), organic and political approaches in urban intervention (urban intervention-organic approaches and, policy-led approaches), and ground-based approaches in ground construction and branding (place based-place making and place branding) [33]; [32]. In line with these evaluations, cultural-oriented urban strategies shaped by cultural planning are examined under three headings. These are cultural neighborhoods, large-scale cultural events and pioneering projects that brand the city [34]; [35]; [36].

The pioneering projects that brand the city consist mainly of symbolic structures and urban design projects and urban strategies aimed at branding and marketing the city in order to attract investments in the competitive environment of the cities and provide economic development. Accordingly, Mommass [37] stated that branding is not only a simple economic activity that adds economic value to the city, but also that the socio-cultural effect of urban branding is important and contributes to urban identity and social integration. Branding in cities is seen in traditional product/production and architectural structures. Branding is designed especially as the places where cultural activities will be held such as architectural structures, art galleries, museums, theater halls and it constitutes the physical infrastructure of culture-based urban strategies [38];

[39]; [40]. Likewise, they are deemed important in mega cultural events, urban transformation, place-making and place marketing strategies ([41].

Culture-based urban renewal approach paves the way for efficient use of cultural resources through encouraging economic activities in cooperation with local governments and local businesses [42]. Cultural investments in urban renewal chiefly concentrate on physical, social, economic, tourism and leisure issues / problems [43].

In the post-1980 economic restructuring process, the importance of cultural policies in the development of countries and transformation of urban spaces increased. In this process, central administrations and local governments have focused on increasing the quality of urban life through culture-oriented development strategies, providing new employment opportunities and creating conditions for social and cultural integration [44]; [45]. However, these objectives lead to homogenization of the urban landscape [46].

Two different accounts draw attention when it comes to the relationship of urban policies with cultural economy. First, it expresses the cultural economy as either a subset of the knowledge or creative economy. Second, it views art and culture as consumption opportunities that will trigger development and improve the image of the city. Both approaches consist of urban and cultural policies that target cultural activities and do not take into consideration the values of cultural production, industrial places and people. Urban policymakers have generally considered the cultural economy an extension of the creative or knowledge-based economy or a means of consumption. Consequently, importance has been placed on programs to lure highly educated and resourceful professionals, as the issue of labor inequality, gentrification, displacement of small and independent manufacturing enterprises persist [47]. While cultural-based urban renewal policies are backed by city administration and public policies, cultural entrepreneurs pioneer the gentrification by transforming old neighborhoods via artistic activities [46]. At this point, Douglass [48] stated that as a consequence of the corporatization and gentrification of creative communities, the social value / meaning of local heritage and cultural production transformed into cultural events and mass-produced imitations of craft products. Ferilli, Sacco & Tavano Blessi [49] stated that only when they create strategies that will comprise different economic, social and environmental issues under the same roof will cultural-based urban renewal policies be successful. Consequently, strategies that will mobilize and involve local communities to create lasting changes in solving urban problems could create sustainable success [43].

2. The Socio-Economic Structure of Van Province

When some statistical data of Van are examined, it is possible to see more clearly the development problem of the city. Van, city, eastern Türkiye, situated on the eastern shore of Lake Van (Fig. 1). Van city with a population of 1,149,342, is in the 75th place out of 81 cities in Türkiye in the socio-economic development index, and it is in the 77th

place in the human development index ranking. In the literacy ranking of Türkiye, it is located in the 68th place. In 2013, the unemployment rate of Van was 10,3%. The total number of protected areas in Van is 80, while the immovable cultural property required to be protected is 178. The city has a history of about 7000 years. Finally, in the industrial sector, Van Region (TRB2) has an industrial production value per capita 11 times lower than the general value in Türkiye. On the other hand, per capita value of gross investment in Van is 10 times lower than the general value in Türkiye [50]; [51]. In addition, there are infrastructure and superstructure problems related to urbanization of Van and lack of equipment for quality of life. According to these data, it is seen that Van city has serious socio-economic development problems. Despite these problems, Van's cultural and natural diversity, as well as its potential to be an important commercial center due to its geopolitical situation, are important for the solution of existing problems.

Fig.1: Geographic Location of Van Province

3. Development Policies and Actors In Van

In 1999, Türkiye's candidacy for full EU membership was accepted. Then, in 2004, the Brussels Summit gave a positive opinion that the political criteria were adequately met. After with the start of Türkiye's exact EU negotiations in 2005, EU has begun to impact on the international development policy as the most effective actor. Regional policies became more important especially with the EU harmonization process. Development Agencies were established in 2006 and Eastern Anatolia Project (EAP) Regional Development Administration was established in 2011 responsible for the planning and implementation of these policies at the regional level. Since 1960, development plans have also been affected by these changes and shifted periodically from statist approaches to free market approaches. In this process, cultural policies have shifted from the emphasis on national culture to the emphasis on cultural diversity along with

the EU harmonization process and have become important in economic and social dimensions.

According to the development objectives determined in the plans and strategies of national actors, the roles determined for Van city are given in Table 1. The roles of these actors which aim to develop Van are as follows: State Planning Organization (SPO)– “Attraction Center” in 2000, Ministry of Culture and Tourism – “Urartu Culture and Tourism Development Zone” in 2007, Ministry of Environment and Urbanism – “Regional Center Based on Trade, Services and Industry Sectors” in 2008, Ministry of Development – “Regional Attraction Center and Cultural Tourism Destinations and Development Zone” in 2014, EAP Regional Development Administration - Attraction Center/Growth Center, Eastern Anatolia Development Agency (EADA) Commercial - Regional Center Based on Services and Industrial Sectors. For these purposes, it is seen that 2 roles are assigned to the City of Van. The first of these is to be the “Regional Center City Based on Trade, Services and Industrial Sectors” as the center of attraction and growth. The second is the “Urartian Culture and Tourism Development Zone” as a tourism center. In light of these, it is understood that a development model for the commercial, services and industrial sectors has been adopted along with the tourism perspective.

Table 1: The role of national actors in Van

YEAR	ACTOR	PLAN/STRATEGY	ROLE
2000	SPO	EAP 2000 Main Plan	Attraction Center
2007-2013	Ministry of Culture and Tourism	Türkiye Tourism Strategy 2023 Action Plan 2007-2013	Urartu Culture and Tourism Development Area
2008	Ministry of Environment and Urbanization	Van, Muş, Bitlis 1/100.000 Environmental Layout Plan	Regional Center Based on Trade, Services and Industrial Sectors
2014	Ministry of Development	National Strategy for Regional Development (NSRD) 2014-2023	Regional Attraction Center and Cultural Tourism Destinations and Development Region
2014	EAP Regional Development	EAP 2014-2018 Action Plan	Attraction Center/Growth Center

Administration

2014	EADA	Regional Plan for TRB2 Region 2014-2023	Regional Center Based on Commercial, Services and Industrial Sectors
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4. Materials and Methods

It is aimed to evaluate Van's development problem on the cultural perspective by examining the actors affecting Van's development and planning process periodically (2003-2016) in the context of grants, supports, investments human development and cultural economy. Accordingly, the grants/subsidies/investments made to Van since 2003 were classified in terms of their contents, in relation to the institutional classification of actors, ISIC REV.4 / NACE REV.2 classification, cultural economy classification and human development index classification.

The study employs content analysis. By examining these data in greater depth, the content analysis aims to reach the concepts, categories, and themes that explain them. In the content analysis, by concentrating on the collected data, codes are constituted in events and facts repeated in the data set or that the participant emphasizes. From codes to categories, and then from categories to themes, data analysis is carried out. In summary, data (codes) determined to be similar and related to each other are brought together within the framework of certain concepts (categories) and themes and elucidated [52]; [53]; [54]; [55]; [56].

The data is inspected and broken down into meaningful sections; finally, what each section means conceptually is revealed in the coding stage. These sections, which form a significant category on their own, are coded by the researcher [57]; [58]. Strauss & Corbin [59] expressed that there are three types of coding. These are as per the following: coding made according to pre-determined concepts, coding made according to the notions extracted from the data, and coding made in a general framework [58] [56].

4.1. Classification of Investments in Van by Sectoral, Cultural Economy and Human Development Index

It is aimed to determine the sectoral, human and cultural dimensions of the investments provided to Van. For this purpose, investments were evaluated in the cultural economy classification developed by ISIC REV.4 / NACE REV.2, UNDP's Human Development Index (HDI) and UNCTAD [28], INTELI [60], Aksoy and Enlil [31].

The Human Development Index (HDI) was elaborated with reference to the work of UNDP [19], Mushkin [61], Schultz [62], Lucas [63] and Sab & Smith [64]. Consequently,

health investments as life expectancy index and educational investments as education index were assessed. In the income index which is included in the human development index, since the GDP per capita indicator is used and there is no such content in investments, this index is not taken into consideration within the scope of the research. In accordance with these evaluations, the Human Development Index is categorized as education, health and education and health on the basis of investments as in Table 2. According to this classification, educational activities comprise school building, vocational and cultural training, capacity building training, human rights training, and vocational training courses. Health activities involve sports activities, the construction of sports complexes, scientific studies for the health sector and infrastructure works for human health [56].

Table 2: Classification of human development index [54]

HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX *		
EDUCATION	HEALTH	EDUCATION AND HEALTH
School construction, vocational and cultural training, community centers, construction of educational centers and cultural centers, infrastructure and superstructure works in schools, strategy reports, feasibility studies, workshops and seminars, training activities for capacity building of institutions and NGOs, vocational personal development training, vocational training courses, human rights education, EU Education Programs (Lifelong Learning and Youth Programs), educational activities for autistic children, educational activities on democracy and human rights.	Sports activities (basketball, volleyball, swimming, etc.), construction of sports facilities (sports complexes and sports fields), R & D studies for the health sector, dialysis center, production of diagnostic laboratory kit, medical plant research, drinking water for human health rehabilitation and treatment systems and sewer construction, patient care, outdoor nature sports, molecular level diagnostic method.	Training activities for the health sector (sports training, human health training, physician training abroad).
*Formed by developing from Mushkin (1962), Schultz (1968), Lucas (1998), Sab & Smith (2001) and UNDP (2015).		

Eventually, the classification for cultural economy was enhanced by UNCTAD [28], INTELI [60], Aksoy and Enlil [31]. In this classification, subclasses are characterized under the headings “cultural heritage”, “art”, “cultural industries” and “creative services”. Investments are assessed in 4 main classes and subclasses of these classes (see Table 3).

4.2. Actors and Financial Support and Grant Programs Provided to Van

The grant support and investment programs provided to Van between 2003 and 2016 are given in Table 4. Accordingly, among the national actors, the Ministry of Development Social Support Program (SSP), the Ministry of Interior Return to the Village and Rehabilitation Project (RVRP), the Ministry of Culture and Tourism Van

Survey and Monuments Directorate, General Directorate of Foundations Bitlis Regional Directorate and EAP Regional Development Administration have realized investments with EADA Support Programs. Among the international actors, the EU provided grant support under the Pre-Accession Financial Assistance Programs and EU Programs.

Table 3: Cultural economy classification [54]

Cultural Economy Classification*	
Classification	Subclasses
1. Cultural Heritage (CH)	<p>It is a collection of tangible and intangible works created by people in the historical process. Tangible heritage includes the historical, natural and cultural structures; intangible cultural heritage covers language, rituals, traditions and cultural expressions.</p> <p><u>1.1. Handicrafts:</u> Jewelry, weaving-textile, ceramics and wood crafts, art restoration and so on.</p> <p><u>1.2. Traditional Gastronomy:</u> It includes eating and drinking culture shaped by traditional methods and cultural structure of society.</p> <p><u>1.3. Historical, cultural and natural heritage (Tangible Heritage):</u> Museums, archives, libraries, archaeological sites (protected areas), monuments, natural parks, nature conservation areas and so on.</p> <p><u>1.4. Traditional Building Materials/Traditional Products:</u> Natural building materials used in Traditional Architecture/Folk Architecture (such as Ahlat stone, travertine, wood, etc.).</p> <p><u>1.5. Intangible Cultural Heritage:</u> Oral traditions and expressions together with the language that acts as a carrier in transferring intangible cultural heritage. Performing arts (traditional music, dances, theaters, etc.), social practices, rituals, festivals, practices and knowledge of the universe and nature.</p>
2. Art (A)	<p><u>2.1. Visual arts: Painting, sculpture contemporary arts, photography.</u></p> <p><u>2.2. Performing Arts: Live music, theater, dance, opera, circus, etc.</u></p>
3. Culture Industries (CI)	<p>It is composed of television, radio, internet broadcasting, press and broadcasting and film industries which can be called as media in broad sense.</p> <p><u>3.1. Publishing and print media</u></p> <p><u>3.2. Radio and Television</u></p> <p><u>3.3. Music Industry</u></p> <p><u>3.4. Film Industry</u></p>
4. Creative Services (CS)	<p>It includes services that require creativity together with cultural and entertainment services.</p> <p><u>4.1. Design: Fashion, interior architecture, graphics, jewelry, etc.</u></p> <p><u>4.2. New Media and Software: Software, video games, content production and management</u></p> <p><u>4.3. Architecture: Architectural services</u></p> <p><u>4.4. Advertising: Advertising Services</u></p> <p><u>4.5. Culture and Entertainment Services: Cultural Centers, festival organizations, cultural activities (trips, festivals, etc.)</u></p>
*Formed by developing from UNCTAD (2008), INTELI (2011), Aksoy & Enlil (2011).	

Table 4: Grant support and investment programs for Van (2003-2016)

NATIONAL ACTORS	GRANT SUPPORT AND INVESTMENT PROGRAMS
MINISTRY OF DEVELOPMENT (MD)	<u>SODES (SOCIAL SUPPORT PROGRAM)</u> Culture, Arts and Sports Component (CAS), Employment Component (EC), Social Inclusion Component (SIC)
MINISTRY OF INTERIOR (MI)	<u>KDRP (RETURN TO VILLAGE AND REHABILITATION PROJECT)</u>
MINISTRY OF CULTURE AND	<u>VAN SURVEY AND MONUMENTS DIRECTORATE</u>

TOURISM (MCT)	
GENERAL DIRECTORATE OF FOUNDATIONS (GDF)	<u>BİTLİS REGIONAL OFFICE</u>
EASTERN ANATOLIA PROJECT (EAP) REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT ADMINISTRATION	<u>COORDINATORSHIPS</u> ¹ Agriculture and Rural Development Coordinator (ARDC), Economic Development, Industry and Services Coordinator (EDISC), Human, Social and Institutional Development Coordinator (HSIDC)
EASTERN ANATOLIA DEVELOPMENT AGENCY (EADA)	<u>SUPPORT PROGRAMS</u> ² Financial Support Program (FSP), Direct Activity Support Program (DASP), Technical Support Program (TSP) and Attraction Center Support Program (ACSP)
INTERNATIONAL ACTORS	GRANT SUPPORT AND INVESTMENT PROGRAMS
European Union (EU)	<u>PRE-ACCESSION FINANCIAL ASSISTANCE PROGRAMS AND EU PROGRAMS</u> ³ . Pre-Accession Financial Assistance (2000-2007), Pre-Accession Financial Assistance Instrument (IPA I) (2007-2013), Pre-Accession Financial Assistance Instrument (IPA II) (2014-2020), EU Programs

4.3. Distribution of the Investments of National and International Actors in Van in Terms of Sectoral Classification, Cultural Economy and Human Development Index

The sectoral classification of actors' projects between 2003 and 2016 according to ISIC REV.4 / NACE REV.2 is given in Table 5. Accordingly, the highest number of projects covers education (411), construction (305) and agriculture, forestry and fisheries (205). According to the classification of cultural economy, more cultural investments took place in agriculture, forestry and fishery (117), education (44) and construction (117) sectors. The distribution of all financial support and grant programs provided to Van by institution classification, cultural economy classification and human development index in terms of actors is given in Table 6. Accordingly, projects belonging to the European Union, which is an international actor, and the national actors, Ministry of Interior, Ministry of Development, General Directorate of Foundations, Ministry of Culture and Tourism, EAP Regional Development Administration and EADA institutions were evaluated within the scope of grant programs and financial supports. Between 2003 and 2016, 479.246.019,18 TL support was provided to 1216 projects in Van. 330 of the 1216 projects were evaluated as cultural investments and constituted 27,69% of the total support with 132.750.892,96 TL support. According to the human development index,

722 of the 1216 projects were evaluated within the scope of human capital and 187.674.966,72 TL was supported. This amount constitutes 39,18% of the total support. The highest cultural investments in Van city are done by EADA, Ministry of Culture and Tourism, General Directorate of Foundations and EAP Regional Development Administration and by central and local actors. The highest investments for human capital were provided by the EU, Ministry of Development and EADA actors. Of the 1216 projects, 546 were run by public institutions, 217 by NGOs, 139 by companies (SMEs), 263 by individuals and 51 by groups. Within the scope of European Union financial support grant programs, 214.448.764,63 TL was provided to 560 projects in Van between 2003 and 2016. 153 of these projects were evaluated in the cultural investment category in line with the criteria adopted in this study. A total of 12.141.909,56 TL was granted to these projects in the cultural category by the EU. This support constitutes 5,67% of the total support provided by the EU in the City of Van. Under the responsibility of the Ministry of Interior at central level and the governorship of Van at local level, 9.560.000,00 TL was provided to 18 projects within the scope of the Return to Village and Rehabilitation Project (RVRP) implemented between 2009 and 2014 in Van. 5 of the 18 projects were evaluated as cultural investments and accounted for 20,71% of the total support with 1.980.000,00 TL support. In the same way, 62.076.119,61 TL was granted to 353 projects under the Social Support Program (SSP) implemented in Van between 2010 and 2015 under the responsibility of the Ministry of Development at the central level and the Governorship of Van at the local level. 72 out of 353 projects were evaluated as cultural investments and 13.462.819,73 TL support to cultural projects constituted 21,69% of the total support. Between 2005 and 2015, 16.149.693,07 TL was invested in 25 projects in Van city under the responsibility and execution of Regional Directorate of Foundations at central level and Bitlis Regional Directorate at local level. In the same way, 27.888.284,67 TL was invested in 34 projects in Van between 2005 and 2016 under the responsibility and execution of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism at the central level and the Directorate of Surveying and Monuments at the local level.

Table 5: Sectoral classification of actors' projects according to ISIC REV.4 / NACE REV.2 between 2003-2016

ISIC REV.4/NACE REV.2		ACTORS															
		MD (SSP)		MI (KVRP)		MCT		GDF		EAP		EADA		EU		TOTAL	
CODE	DESCRIPTION	NG P	CEP	NG P	CEP	NG P	CEP	NGP	CEP	NG P	CEP	NGP	CEP	NGP	CEP	NGP	CEP
A	AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND FISHERIES	1								2		12	2	190	115	205	117
B	MINING AND QUARRYING											2	2			2	2
C	PRODUCTION											59	2	78	7	137	9
E	WATER SUPPLY; SEWAGE, WASTE MANAGEMENT AND IMPROVEMENT ACTIVITIES											1		5		6	0
F	CONSTRUCTION	151	42	13	3	27	27	25	25	10	2	31	11	48	7	305	117
G	WHOLESALE AND RETAIL TRADE; REPAIRS OF MOTOR VEHICLES AND MOTORCYCLES											1	1	1		2	1

Table 5: Sectoral classification of actors' projects according to ISIC REV.4 / NACE REV.2 between 2003-2016

ISIC REV.4/NACE REV.2		ACTORS																	
		MD (SSP)		MI (KVRP)		MCT		GDF		EAP		EADA		EU		TOTAL			
CODE	DESCRIPTION	NG P	CEP	NG P	CEP	NG P	CEP	NGP	CEP	NG P	CEP	NGP	CEP	NGP	CEP	NGP	CEP		
H	TRANSPORTATION AND STORAGE													1		1		2	0
I	ACCOMMODATION AND FOOD SERVICE ACTIVITIES	2		1										2	1	3	2	8	3
J	INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION													5	3	3	2	8	5
M	PROFESSIONAL, SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL ACTIVITIES					7	7					8	4	19	6	2	1	36	18
N	ADMINISTRATIVE AND SUPPORT SERVICE ACTIVITIES															3		3	0
P	EDUCATION	146	24	3	1							1		65	7	196	12	411	44
Q	HUMAN HEALTH AND SOCIAL WORK ACTIVITIES			1	1									7		5		13	1
R	CULTURE, ART, ENTERTAINMENT, RECREATION AND SPORT	53	6													3	3	56	9
S	OTHER SERVICE ACTIVITIES															22	4	22	4
TOTAL		353	72	18	5	34	34	25	25	21	6	205	35	560	153	1216	330		

EU: European Union, EADA Eastern Anatolia Development Agency, EAP: Eastern Anatolia Project Regional Department, MCT: Ministry of Culture and Tourism (Van Survey and Monuments Directorate), GDF: General Directorate of Foundations (Bitlis Regional Directorate), MD: Ministry of Development (Social Support Program:SSP), MI: Ministry of Interior (Return to Village and Rehabilitation Project:RVRP) NGP: Number of General Projects CEP: Cultural Economy Projects

Table 6: Distribution of national and international actors' financial support and grant schemes according to culture economy and human development index classification

INVESTMENTS ACCORDING TO CORPORATE CLASSIFICATION						CULTURAL INVESTMENTS ACCORDING TO THE CULTURE ECONOMY CLASSIFICATION			INVESTMENTS ACCORDING TO HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX CLASSIFICATION		
RESPONSIBLE INSTITUTION	FINANCIAL SUPPORT PROGRAMS	DATE	CITY	PROJECT COUNT	GRANT SUPPORT (TL)	PROJECT COUNT	GRANT SUPPORT (TL)	% DISTRIBUTION	PROJECT COUNT	GRANT SUPPORT (TL)	% DISTRIBUTION
EUROPEAN UNION (EU)	Pre-Accession Financial Assistance (2000-2007) Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance IPA I (2007-2013) Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance IPA II (2014-2020) EU Programs	2003-2016	VAN	560	214.448.764,63	153	12.141.909,56	5.67	317	114.710.891,22	53.23
MINISTRY OF INTERIOR (MI) - Van Governorship	Return to Village and Rehabilitation Project (RVRP)	2009-2014	VAN	18	9.560.000,00	5	1.980.000,00	20.71	17	9.210.000,00	96.34
MINISTRY OF DEVELOPMENT (MD) - Van Governorship	Social Support Program (SSP)	2010-2015	VAN	353	62.076.119,60	72	13.462.819,73	21.69	297	53.027.800,01	85.42

Table 6: Distribution of national and international actors' financial support and grant schemes according to culture economy and human development index classification

INVESTMENTS ACCORDING TO CORPORATE CLASSIFICATION						CULTURAL INVESTMENTS ACCORDING TO THE CULTURE ECONOMY CLASSIFICATION			INVESTMENTS ACCORDING TO HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX CLASSIFICATION		
RESPONSIBLE INSTITUTION	FINANCIAL SUPPORT PROGRAMS	DATE	CITY	PROJECT COUNT	GRANT SUPPORT (TL)	PROJECT COUNT	GRANT SUPPORT (TL)	% DISTRIBUTION	PROJECT COUNT	GRANT SUPPORT (TL)	% DISTRIBUTION
GENERAL DIRECTORATE OF FOUNDATIONS (GDF) - Bitlis Regional Directorate	Strategic Objective 3 specified in the Strategic Plan for the 2015-2019 Period	2005-2015	VAN	25	16.149.693,07	25	16.149.693,07	100	0	0	0
MINISTRY OF CULTURE AND TOURISM (MCT) - Van Survey and Monuments Directorate	Strategic Objective 1 stated in the Strategic Plan for 2015-2019 Period	2005-2015	VAN	34	27.888.284,67	34	27.888.284,67	100	0	0	0
Eastern Anatolia Project (EAP) Regional Development Administration	ARDC EDISC HSIDC	2013-2016	VAN	21	22.806.562,35	6	9.448.645,00	41.43	12	4.278.146,86	18.76
Eastern Anatolia Development Agency (EADA)	FSP DASP TSP ACSP	2009-2015	VAN	205	126.316.594,86	35	51.654.542,81	40.89	79	7.014.228,16	5.55
GRAND TOTAL	ALL PROGRAMS	2003-2016	VAN	1216	479.246.019,18	330	132.725.892,18	27.69	722	187.674.966,72	39.18

All these investments were evaluated as culture-oriented investments. A total of 282.171.752,97 TL grants were provided to 42 projects in Van and the cities including EAP cities between 2013 and 2016 under the responsibility of EAP Regional Development Administration, and 41.852.973,04 TL support was provided to 12 projects considered cultural investments within this support and this amount was 14,83% of the total support. In Van alone, 21 projects were supported with TL 22.806.562,35 and 6 of these projects were granted as cultural investment and given 9.448.645,00 TL support. This support amounted to 41,43% of the total support provided by the EAP Regional Development Administration in Van.

Under the responsibility of EADA, between 2009 and 2015, a total of 187.973.193.34 TL was granted to 516 projects in cities including Van, Bitlis, Hakkari and Muş. Within this support, 82 projects which are considered cultural investments were given 67.480.278,17 TL and this figure amounted to 35,90% of the total support. In Van alone, support was provided to 205 projects amounting to 126.316.594,86 TL. 35 of these projects have been evaluated within the scope of cultural investment. A total of 51.654.542,81 TL was granted to these projects within the scope of cultural investment and this amount amounted to 40,89% of the total support.

4.4. Distribution of Van Projects by Actors and Investment Subjects

In line with the above analyses, the topics of cultural investments are important in terms of understanding the nature of the investments and the roles that the actors have determined for development and Van. In this context, cultural projects were analyzed according to investment subjects and classified and evaluated under the headings of physical infrastructure, restoration, activity, content, cultural-human, traditional/agricultural production and traditional building material production. According to this classification: Physical infrastructure projects include cultural and youth centers, women's centers, museums, landscaping of historical sites, movie theaters and theaters, libraries, kilim workshops, wood products processing workshops, silverwork workshops, and buildings agricultural products of high gastronomic value (walnut, honey, pearl mullet/fish cheese, Norduz sheep) production, processing and marketing. Restoration projects include restoration of tangible heritage values (historical, cultural and natural). Events include festivals and concerts. The content includes tourism strategies and feasibility plans for the preservation and promotion of tangible heritage values, sector analysis and strategies in the context of agricultural production (milk, cheese, local products), film screenings, book printing, cultural tourism strategy plans for survival of intangible cultural heritage and model making. Cultural humanitarian projects include training in agricultural production (Norduz sheep breeding, beekeeping), traditional home cooking courses, handicraft courses (rugs, marbling, woodwork, pottery, gold and other handicrafts), language education

(Kurdish), creative drama education, miniature and folk-dance education, theater, painting, music, photography education, environmental education and journalism education. Traditional agricultural production projects and traditional building material production projects constitute livestock farming, animal donation (Norduz sheep and bee) and marble production for farmer groups and real persons based on agricultural production.

In line with this classification, the data regarding the distribution of the projects belonging to Van by investment subjects are given in Table 7. Accordingly, 75,51% of the 330 projects are cultural heritage, 7,63% are arts, 1,26% are cultural industries, 13,55% are creative services, 1,13% are cultural heritage and creative services, 0,50% are cultural heritage and art, 0,23% are cultural heritage and cultural industries and finally 0,19% are the cultural industries and art. The highest investment was transferred to projects in the class of cultural heritage and creative services.

When the functional distribution of grants and investments is considered, of the 80 projects, 48 of them are cultural heritage, 4 of them are arts, 6 of them are cultural industries, 1 of them is cultural industries and arts and 21 of them are creative services. Within the scope of the restoration, 33 of the 50 projects were classified as cultural heritage and 17 of them were classified as cultural heritage and creative services. As a cultural activity, 1 of the 3 projects was evaluated as cultural industries and arts, and 2 as creative services. Of the 16 projects covered, 9 of them are cultural heritage, 4 of them are cultural industries, 1 of them is creative services and 2 of them are cultural heritage and cultural industries. Of 114 projects within the scope of cultural heritage, traditional/agricultural production and 2 projects were evaluated as traditional structural production investments. Accordingly, 60,06% of 330 projects are physical infrastructure, 26,04% are restoration, 7,04% are cultural and human investments, 4,56% are traditional/agricultural production, 1,75% are content, 0,38% are traditional building material production and finally 0,14% are efficiency.

Finally, EADA supported physical infrastructure, cultural-human and content projects mostly; on the other hand, the Ministry of Development and Ministry of Internal Affairs provided supports to physical infrastructure and cultural-human projects especially. When it comes to the General Directorate of Foundations and the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, they backed restoration projects more. Last but not least, the EU provided more support to traditional agricultural production and cultural-human projects in Van province (see Table 8).

Table 7: Distribution of the projects of Van by investment subjects

ACCORDING TO CULTURAL ECONOMY	ACCORDING TO FUNCTIONS							
	PHYSICAL INFRASTRUCTURE	RESTORATION	ACTIVITY	CONTENT	CULTURAL-HUMAN	TRADITIONAL/AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION	TRADITIONAL BUILDING MATERIAL PRODUCTION	TOTAL (TL)
Cultural Heritage (CH)	48 PROJECTS (55.373.399,05 TL)	33 PROJECTS (33.053.840,92 TL)	-	9 PROJECTS (1.534.653,37 TL)	38 PROJECTS (3.812.264,49 L)	114 PROJECTS (6.054.945,27 TL)	2 PROJECTS (394.977,49 TL)	244 PROJECTS (100.224.080,59 TL)
Art (A)	4 PROJECTS (5.802.697,00 TL)	-	-	-	21 PROJECTS (4.321.428,90 TL)	-	-	25 PROJECTS (10.124.125,90 TL)
Cultural Heritage and Art (CH+A)	-	-	-	-	4PROJECTS (663.160,00 TL)	-	-	4 PROJECTS (663.160,00 TL)
Cultural Industries (CI)	6 PROJECTS (630.813,46 TL)	-	-	4 PROJECTS (495.683,45 TL)	2 PROJECTS (542.186,93 TL)	-	-	12 PROJECTS (1.668.683,84 TL)
Cultural Industries and Art (CI+A)	1 PROJECTS (140.575,00 TL)	-	1 PROJECTS (113.800,00 TL)	-	-	-	-	2 PROJECTS (254.375,00 TL)
Creative Services (CS)	21 PROJECTS (17.764.592,06 TL)	-	2 PROJECTS (184.217,55 TL)	1PROJECTS (34.810,00 TL)	-	-	-	24 PROJECTS (17.983.619,61 TL)

Table 7: Distribution of the projects of Van by investment subjects

ACCORDING TO CULTURAL ECONOMY	ACCORDING TO FUNCTIONS							
	PHYSICAL INFRASTRUCTURE	RESTORATION	ACTIVITY	CONTENT	CULTURAL-HUMAN	TRADITIONAL/AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION	TRADITIONAL BUILDING MATERIAL PRODUCTION	TOTAL (TL)
Cultural Heritage and Creative Services (CH+CS)	-	17 PROJECTS (1.505.374,00 TL)	-		-	-	-	17 PROJECTS (1.505.374,00 TL)
Cultural Heritage and Cultural Industries (CH+CI)	-	-	-	2PROJECTS 303.473,58 TL)	-	-	-	2 PROJECTS 303.473,58 TL)
TOTAL	80 PROJECTS (79.712.076,57 TL)	50 PROJECTS (34.559.214,93 TL)	3 PROJECTS (298.017,55 TL)	16 PROJECTS (2.368.620,40 TL)	65 PROJECTS (9.338.040,02 TL)	114 PROJECTS (6.054.945,27 TL)	2 PROJECTS (394.977,49 TL)	330 PROJECTS (132.725.892,18 TL)

CH: Cultural Heritage, CI: Cultural Industries, CS: Creative Services, A: Art

Table 8: Distribution of projects in Van by actors and investment subjects

ACCORDING TO FUNCTIONS							
PHYSICAL INFRASTRUCTURE	RESTORATION	ACTIVITY	CONTENT	CULTURAL-HUMAN	TRADITIONAL/AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION	TRADITIONAL BUILDING MATERIAL PRODUCTION	TOTAL (TL)
10 PROJECTS EADA (48.048.506,06 TL)	4 PROJECTS EADA (2.904.644,30 TL)	2 PROJECTS SSP (139.150,00 TL)	8 PROJECTS EADA (398.392,93 TL)	11 PROJECTS EADA (410.221,93 TL)	114 PROJECTS EU (6.054.945,27 TL)	2 PROJECTS EADA (394.977,49 TL)	35 PROJECTS EADA (51.654.542,81 TL)
3 PROJECTS EAP (8.530.788,43 TL)	21PROJECTS MCT (15.674.438,01TL)	1 PROJECT EU (158.867,55 TL)	3 PROJECTS EAP (917.856,57 TL)	26 PROJECTS SSP (6.071.977,60 TL)			6 PROJECTS EAP (9.448.645,00 TL)
44 PROJECTSSSP (7.251.692,13TL)	24 PROJECTS GDF (16.032.283,07 TL)		1 PROJECT MCT (34.810,00 TL)	2 PROJECTS RVRP (480.000,00 TL)			72 PROJECTS SSP (13.462.819,73 TL)
3 PROJECTS RVRP (1.500.000,00 TL)	1 PROJECT EU (450.049,55 TL)		4 PROJECTS EU (1.017.560,90 TL)	26 PROJECTS EU (2.375.840,49 TL)			5 PROJECTS RVRP (1.980.000,00 TL)
12 PROJECTS MCT (12.179.034,66 TL)							34 PROJECTS MCT (27.888.282,67 TL)
1 PROJECT GDF (117.410,00 TL)							25 PROJECTS GDF (16.149.693,07 TL)
7 PROJECTS EU (2.084.645,29 TL)							153 PROJECTS EU (12.141.909,56 TL)
80 PROJECTS (79.712.076,57 TL)	50 PROJECTS (34.559.214,93 TL)	3 PROJECTS (298.017,55 TL)	16 PROJECTS (2.368.620,40TL)	65 PROJECTS (9.338.040,02 TL)	114 PROJECTS (6.054.945,27 TL)	2 PROJECTS (394.977,49 TL)	330 PROJECTS (132.725.892,18 TL)

EU: European Union, EADA: Eastern Anatolia Development Agency, EAP: Eastern Anatolia Project Regional Department, MCT: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, GDF: General Directorate of Foundations, SSP: Social Support Program (Ministry of Development), RVRP: Return to Village and Rehabilitation Project (Ministry of Interior)

5. Results: Where Is The Culture in Development?

The concept of development that has changed in the world after the middle of the 20th century has turned into a structure that takes human capital into consideration. With this structure, the economic structure (culture economy) based on technology, knowledge, creativity and culture has started to be implemented in cities through culture-based urban strategies.

In this process in Türkiye, with the change in the understanding of development after 1980 and the diversification of the actors directing the development, it is observed that the changes in the cultural perspective have been experienced and that the culture has been instrumentalized as an investment area if not directly but indirectly. According to this, the EU as the international actor and the Ministry of Development, the Ministry of Interior, the Ministry of Tourism and Culture, the General Directorate of Foundations, the EAP and the EADA as the national actors are seen to be important actors in the development policies for the city of Van. It is seen that the strategies of these institutions in line with the objectives they have adopted, match up with the supports they have provided.

The Urartu Museum and Tuşba Fair Center projects, which EADA has made as an investment in Van, within the scope of the Attraction Center Support Program, aim to make an important contribution to the city in terms of architectural design. Especially Urartian Museum exhibits the flag-ship project image with the difference in architectural structure as well as museum function as a cultural structure. Similarly, Tuşba Fair Center can be evaluated in this category. These two projects are tangible indicators that Van city is considered a center of attraction and tourism.

Supported by the Ministry of Development in the cultural investments of Van in line with its development policies, SSP includes construction of cultural centers, theaters, painting and music courses, vocational training courses within the scope of handicrafts and socio-cultural activities for social and cultural development and employment reasons. Accordingly, it is seen that the Ministry of Development attaches importance to human capital in its development approach. The Ministry undertakes both physical and human investments in culture within the scope of this program. Accordingly, it can be stated that the Ministry attaches importance to cultural development with its direct investments in culture within the scope of SSP along with the economic and human development perspective in development.

As cultural investments, the EAP Regional Development Administration supports investments in branding of local products in the rural and human development, building libraries and providing tourism with cultural heritage values. In these investments, cultural values are instrumentalized for rural development and tourism. On the TRB2 level, EADA investments support rural development policies in order to promote and improve local products. In addition, the construction of fairs and museums, the preservation of historical, cultural and natural heritage, promotion and acquisition of tourism shows that the role of attraction and cultural tourism center at regional level has been adopted and implemented. It is evident that SSP makes direct investments in culture but culture is evaluated in light of tourism and rural development in EAP and EADA investments.

The RVRP, supported by the Ministry of Interior in order to reduce and improve the negative effects of the socio-economic problems of Van city and especially the terrorist incidents in the Eastern Anatolia Region, includes investments for social, cultural aspects and employment. In these investments, culture is included in the framework of rural development and tourism. The EU, which is the most important international actor, reflects EU regional policies with its support for the City of Van. The projects considered cultural investment in support programs include rural development, social development and human development policies for employment. It is seen that the supports provided by taking into consideration the socio-economic dimension of Van city have been invested in human capital.

When we look at the relationship between national and international actors; Ministry of Development, EAP Regional Development Administration EAP Regional Administration Presidency and EADA are in harmony with the development targets set in national and regional plans. In line with these plans, the grants provided to the city of Van are aimed at Van's being "Attraction Center, Regional Attraction Center and Regional Center City Based on Commercial, Services and Industrial Sectors". It is seen that the targets of "Cultural Tourism Destinations and Development Zones" and "Urartu Culture and Tourism Development Zones" overlap between the Ministry of Development and the Ministry of Culture and Tourism and investments have been made with intentions for these targets. Within the scope of EU regional policies, in line with the target of "Regional Attraction Centers", Regional Competitiveness Operational Programme (RCOP) and Competitiveness and Innovation Sector Operational Programme (CISOP) projects and IPARD (Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance Rural Development) rural development projects are in line with the EAP Regional Development Administration and EADA's regional policies and investments. In addition, the Ministry of the Interior's "Return to Village Rehabilitation Project (RVRP)"

and the “Economic and Social Integration of internally displaced persons in Van City” of the EU, have provided grants to IDPs for the same purpose. The General Directorate of Foundations made investments in line with its corporate objectives. An important point here is that the investments made by each actor according to their own policies and the investments of other actors should support each other. For this structure, the relationship between the actors should be clearer. In general, the development problem of Van city is evaluated from two perspectives on the basis of national actors. The first of these is a development model within the scope of industry, trade and services, which is mainly based on the economic dimension of development. The other is a development model from the perspective of tourism in the services class. These two models are sometimes evaluated together and sometimes separately. The EU, which is one of the international actors, evaluates the development problem of Van from the perspective of human and social development within the scope of rural development. In the study, it can be said that development in Van is not directly evaluated from the cultural perspective, but the culture is mostly handled with tourism. Accordingly, a development through tourism includes cultural values and indirectly affects cultural development.

National and international actors, though not directly but indirectly, see culture as an area of investment. However, when we look at the current development problems of Van, it cannot be said that only a development from the cultural perspective will be sufficient and successful because the economic, social, cultural and human structures that constitute the four components of improvement have not developed sufficiently for Van. Investments made solely to improve the economic structure will not provide a holistic development by ignoring the human, social and cultural dimension, and investments in culture alone, will not provide the desired development by disregarding other developmental dimensions. So, if the people living in Van have a not good enough socio-economic condition (below the average of Türkiye according to HDI and Socio-Economic Development Index), contribution in the social, human and cultural activities will not be sufficient. First of all, it is necessary to improve and develop the economic structure and then to support other dimensions of development.

As a result, the development problem of Van city manifests itself not only in the economic dimension but also in the human and social dimensions. Especially in the roles determined by national and international actors for Van, development is not considered a whole together with its economic, social, human and cultural dimensions. Each actor creates policies according to his/her own mission and supports these policies with investments. Therefore, different development tools have been developed for Van. What is crucial at this point is that in the economic development model

adopted/envisaged for each role, a structure that nurtures cultural, social and human capital, together with different development tools, is implemented in integrity (not piece by piece). When this model is formed, tourism potential for Van's cultural, natural and historical structure, industrial and commercial center function and human capital potential will be integrated and development will not be provided from a single perspective but will become a system that nourishes itself by diversifying over multiple perspectives. Together with this system, the cultural policies that will be established in line with the economic, social and cultural structure of Van will gain more meaning and develop in the local area.

Notes:

1. *Agriculture and Rural Development Coordination Grant Scheme includes: Small Scale Agricultural Irrigation Program (TSP), Animal Drinking Water (HIS) Pond Program, Crop Development Infrastructure Development Project (DAP), Agricultural Infrastructure Development Project, Licensed Livestock Market Project, DAP Region Strengthening the Physical Infrastructure of Research and Application Units of Agricultural and Veterinary Faculties, Establishment of Farmer Training Centers, Improving Institutional and Human Capacity Project, Improving Institutional Capacity Project and Improving Fruit Production Project, Regional Ovine Breeding Project, Watering Place Distribution Project, Determination of Sub - Region in Rural Development of Ağrı and Preparation of Rural Development Plan. In 2015, five projects were carried out by the Economic Development, Industry and Services Coordination Department. These are: Entrepreneurship and Innovation Needs Analysis Project, Determination of Localization Commercialization Strategies Project, Development of Recreation Areas in DAP Region, Various Survey Project (Renewable Energy Project) and Eastern Anatolia Winter Tourism Strategy Project. In 2015, six programs and projects were carried out by the Human, Social and Institutional Development Coordination Department. These are: Economic and Social Development Program for the Border Districts of the DAP Region (SESKAP), District Libraries Project, City Libraries Project, Urartu Culture Corridor Project, DAP Spiritual Personalities Program and DAP Cities Cultural Assets Inventories and Mucitbank Project ([65]; [66].*

2. *Between 2009 and 2015, 12 programs were implemented within the scope of DAKA Financial Support Programs. These are: Model Cattle Farming Expansion Financial Support Program, Small Scale Infrastructure Financial Support Program for Strengthening Investment Infrastructure, Encouraging the Use of Renewable Energy Resources Financial Support Program, Fruit and Vegetable Improvement in Hakkari City, Financial Support Program for Small Scale Infrastructure Projects for Strengthening Investment and Tourism Infrastructure (2013, 2015), Economic Development Financial Support Program, Strong Entrepreneurship Financial Support Program, Small Scale Infrastructure Projects Financial Support Program for Strengthening Faith Tourism Infrastructure in Hakkari, the Financial Support Program for the Promotion of Competitiveness and the Financial Support Program for the Support of Small Entrepreneurship [67].*

3. *The projects supported in Van have received support under Pre-Accession Financial Assistance (Pre-IPA and IPA I-II) and EU Programs. Pre-accession programs implemented as financial assistance program: MEDA Program, Promotion of Civil Society Dialogue between the European Union and Türkiye (STD - I) Pre-Aide to the 2004 Financial Assistance Programs (Active Labor Market Strategy Program Grant Scheme, New Opportunities Program) IPA I Component 3 Regional Development (Regional Competitiveness Professional Program (BROP), Environmental Operational Program (ESC), IPA I Component 1 (Transition Assistance and Institutional*

Structuring Component (Civil Society Dialogue II-III), Displaced Persons in Van City Economic and Social Integration Grant Program (Van-IDP), Strengthening Preschool Education Grant Program, Türkiye's Women in Underdeveloped Regions and the Empowerment of Women NGOs Grant Program, IPA II Component 4 (Development Component of Human Resources) (Supporting Lifelong Learning, Promoting Registered Employment, Youth Employment Support, Increasing Schooling Especially for Girls, Promoting Women Employment, IPA I Component 5 (Rural Development Component (Rural Development Operational Program (IPARD Program)), IPA II Component 2 (Regional Development-Competitiveness and Innovation Sector Operational Program (RYSOP)) As EU Programs: Lifelong Learning and Youth Programs (Comenius, Leonardo, Erasmus, Youth Exchanges), the EU Competitiveness and Innovation Program (CIP) and the European Instrument for Democracy and Human Rights (EIDHR).

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